

Counter-storytelling of La Raza at the Borderlands of race, language, and mathematics

Stacy R. Jones, The University of Texas at Austin, ✉ srjones@utexas.edu

Carlos Nicolas Gomez Marchant, The University of Texas at Austin

Hangil Kim, The University of Texas at Austin

Gerardo Sánchez Gutiérrez, The University of Texas at Austin

*Through composite counter-storytelling, we share the collective experiences of Raza learners that highlight the relentlessness of racism and linguisticism within white institutional spaces. We highlight the experiences of 11 fourth grade Raza learners who find themselves within the Borderlands of Raza and Anglo cultures. We use Borderlands, a space of inbetweenness, to foreground the mathematical experiences, contradictions, and ways of resisting in relation to race and language for Raza learners. We argue Raza learners should be able to embrace themselves as inhabiting Borderlands and be guided towards a path of *conocimiento*, where a deeper understanding of themselves and their place in the world produces knowledge from their unique perspectives.*

Introduction

We have been gifted the opportunity to learn with 46 Raza¹ students in grades 3–5 and recognize the privilege and urgency to share their experiential knowledge with others in order to create more equitable spaces. This collaboration has pushed us to think more deeply about the experiences of Raza learners inhabiting predominantly white spaces, both numerically and ideologically. Therefore, we feel a responsibility to not only acknowledge their contributions to this work, but also share their experiential knowledge within a larger community working towards social justice. In this paper, we share the development of a composite counter-story of 11 Raza fourth grade students and their experiences learning mathematics while navigating white institutional spaces.

White institutional spaces refer to the “ideologies, discourses, and practices in [spaces which] serve to privilege white perspectives, white ideological frames, white power, and white dominance all the while purporting to represent [the spaces] as neutral and objective”

¹ We use Raza and La Raza as a political tool to disrupt the oppressive nature of Latinx and Hispanic being imposed on Raza communities and perpetuating Eurocentric storylines (see Anzaldúa, 1987; Martínez, 2017; Gutiérrez, 2001).

Please cite as: Jones, S. R., Gomez Marchant, C., N., Kim, H., & Sánchez Gutiérrez, G. (2021). Counter-storytelling of La Raza at the Borderlands of race, language, and mathematics. In D. Kolloche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 526–534). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5414310>

(Martin, 2015, p. 443). One way our society creates white institutional spaces is through the use of storytelling. Anglos have centred their experiences and ways of knowing as Truth and passed down their stories through academic and non-academic spaces such as school, history classes, books, media, and news outlets. They have silenced the stories, experiences, and ways of knowing of People of Color and positioned our knowledge as un-American, unpatriotic, reverse racism, untrue, and inferior. Furthermore, storytelling from an Anglo-only perspective perpetuates white saviour narratives, protects white culture, and encourages the healing of genocide, war, and slavery by forgetting, avoiding, and providing inaccurate information.

Some cultures have been able to assimilate into the dominant culture and become white (see Yancey, 2004; Ignatiev, 2009). Yancey (2004) argued that in order for a culture (or person) to become white, they must repudiate their ancestral cultural values, and then adopt the beliefs, language, customs, and narratives of white culture. For example, the Irish are now recognized as white and part of the dominant culture due to their skin colour, adoption of dominant ideologies of a superior white race by perpetuating racial hierarchies, and abandoning their ancestral Irish culture (Ignatiev, 2009). When the United States claims all are welcome, it is on the condition that those from other cultures will strive to become white and take up the white culture dominant within the United States.

However, when cultures do not adopt the values of the dominant culture and instead choose to maintain their own cultural values and strive for equitable spaces, the dominant culture responds with *white rage* (Anderson, 2017) and keeps these communities on the margins of society. A recent example of white rage is the insurrection on the United States' capitol building on January 6, 2021 where white supremacists attacked with intentions to hinder the official counting of votes for a new president. White rage can also be seen when slavery was banned in the American south and African Americans tried to move to the northern US for more opportunities, but "white Southerners saw black advancement and independence as a threat to their culture, and, indeed, their economy" (Anderson, 2017, p. 46) and created laws preventing the recruitment of African Americans for employment in the north.

The process of schooling in the United States is a project to ensure students are provided the necessary skills to assimilate into white institutional spaces (Martin, 2015) or become more white (Carbado & Gulati, 2014). Students who are not part of the dominant culture are expected to assimilate into the dominant culture and forego any aspects of other cultures (Orozco, 2012). Students who learn to assimilate are considered successful and good students; whereas students who preserve an ancestral culture and values are seen as uneducable and burdens on society (Martinez, 2020). Furthermore, students from non-dominant cultures must traverse through multiple cultures, making sense of the tensions, contradictions, and experiences of not being fully part of one or the other, but located in between cultures.

Raza communities, however, must navigate discrimination based on race and language and are dehumanized in various ways despite our degree of assimilation into Anglo cultural

values and language. Flores and Rosa (2015) describe raciolinguistic ideologies as “conflat[ing] certain racialized bodies with linguistic deficiency unrelated to any objective linguistic practices” (p. 150). Therefore, placing Raza learners in contradictory spaces, where schools ask Raza students to assimilate, while also preventing them from ever fully reaching whiteness due to “looking like a language and sounding like a race” (Rosa, 2019, p. 2). Raza students are habitually othered due to their skin colour determining their linguistic repertoire as well as their linguistic repertoire positioning them as Other.

We share the development of a composite counter-story (Solórzano & Yosso, 2002; Yosso, 2006) of the tensions, contradictions, and ways of resisting while learning and doing mathematics as described by a few Raza learners. We aim to emphasize how white institutional spaces are not made with Raza communities in mind and therefore need to be revealed, questioned, and disrupted. We use Latinx critical theory to frame our exploration into how Raza students are racialized as well as provide our methodology of composite counter-storytelling (Solórzano & Yosso, 2002; Yosso, 2006). We couple Latinx critical theory with Borderlands theory (Anzaldúa, 1987) to explore how white supremacy and racism develop tensions and contradictions at the borderlands. These frameworks complement one another to centre the voices and unique experiences of Raza, challenge dominant narratives of how race and language play a role in the learning and doing of mathematics, and work for more socially just spaces for Raza students.

Theoretical framings

Latinx critical theory framed our exploration of Raza students’ experiences in predominantly white spaces, allowing us to reveal how race and language are used to position Raza as inferior in a racial hierarchy. We overlap Anzaldúa’s (1987) work on Borderlands theory with Latinx critical theory to dig deeper into how Raza students are navigating white spaces as a hybrid of Raza and Anglo cultures. In the following sections we describe each of these theoretical frameworks in more detail.

Latinx critical theory

Latinx critical theory guided our exploration to understand the lived experiences of Raza students in predominantly white spaces (see Solórzano & Yosso, 1998; 2001; 2002). Latinx critical theory is an extension of critical race theory to focus on how Raza communities are racialized due to phenotype, surname, language, and citizenship (Flores, 2018; Yosso, 2006). The tenets of critical race theory vary; however, the following tenets guide our work: 1) race is a social construct and racism is endemic in our society; 2) challenging dominant ideology; 3) centring experiential knowledge of People of Color; 4) progress towards change happens through interest convergence with the dominant culture; 5) commitment to social justice; and 6) the use of interdisciplinary studies (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017; Solórzano et al., 1998). Next, we briefly describe each tenet and how they inform our work.

Critical race theory is conceptualized through ethnic studies, women studies, and anthropology in order to highlight how racism impacts the experiences of People of Color.

Anglos positioned themselves as superior through their words and actions that dehumanize indigenous people, Africans and African Americans, and Raza communities through genocide, slavery, and war (Dunbar-Ortiz, 1994). Race is socially constructed in order to establish a dominant culture (middle- and upper-class Anglo males) in all aspects of our lives: education, labour, society, and politics. Furthermore, Solórzano and Yosso (2002) described critical race methodology that puts into action critical race theory in education by challenging dominant narratives, centring the voices of People of Color through intersectional lenses, and working towards social justice. Critical race scholars caution, however, that the dominant culture will not willingly give up control, but progress is only made when there is benefit to the dominant culture as well, or an interest convergence (see Bell, 2018). Latinx critical theory provides a specific lens to understand how the previously mentioned tenets are experienced within Raza communities. We use Borderlands theory in conjunction with Latinx critical theory to think more critically about the conflicting spaces Raza students must navigate in a white supremacist society and predominantly white schools.

Borderlands theory

Anzaldúa (1987) conceptualized Borderlands theory through her lived experiences growing up at the Mexico-U.S. borderland which forced her to traverse multiple cultures where she was neither fully immersed in a Mexican culture or an Anglo culture, but a hybrid of the two. Anzaldúa used borderlands to represent the physical borderland separating land either naturally (e.g., oceans, rivers) or unnaturally (e.g., walls). On the other hand, Borderland with an uppercase “B” is described as the emotional state of inhabiting a space of inbetweenness, or *nepantla*, which refers to the multiple cultures she inhabited. Anzaldúa highlights the unique perspective and lived experiences of those navigating Borderlands where knowledge can be gained through the complications of being both/and as opposed to one or the other. She argued “borders are set up to define the places that are safe and unsafe, to distinguish *us* from *them*...a borderland is a vague and undetermined place created by the emotional residue of an unnatural boundary” (p. 3). It is a space of the unknown, created and determined by each person living within multiple cultures “where one does not know whether to assimilate, separate, or isolate from the demands of the dominant culture” (Aguilar-Valdez et al., 2013, p. 829). Inhabiting a Borderland means one is not fully accepted within either culture but must navigate both cultures simultaneously, creating a new culture from knowledges and experiences within this space of inbetweenness. Anzaldúa (1987) described this duality in terms of Mexican-Americans living at the Mexico-U.S. border:

Nosotros los Chicanos straddle the Borderlands. On one side of us, we are constantly exposed to the Spanish of the Mexicans, on the other side we hear the Anglo’s incessant clamouring so that we forget our language...This voluntary (yet forced) alienation makes for physiological conflict, a kind of dual identity—we don’t identify with the Anglo-American cultural values and we don’t totally identify with the Mexican cultural values. We are a synergy of cultures with various degrees of Mexicanness or Angloness (p. 63).

Raza in the U.S. are neither one nor the other, but a hybrid of the two cultures, both Anglo and Mexican cultures influence ways of being, knowing, and understanding the world. Anzaldúa argued, because of this hybridity and influence of multiple cultures, experiences, and knowledges, nepantleras (those inhabiting Borderlands) are uniquely positioned to create and provide new knowledge.

Borderlands theory is a process one encounters when they are perpetually othered:

Social hierarchies presuppose that the world is composed by rigid and definite categories of superiority and inferiority, where superiority is commonly associated with folks who are white, Christian, middle or upper classes while inferiority is related to those who fall outside of the previous category and are considered different or defective (Orozco-Mendoza, 2008, p. 42).

Inhabiting a Borderlands means one goes through a process beginning with an *arrebato*, or a trauma such as being othered due to skin colour or language. Once an *arrebato* is experienced, Anzaldúa described a person enters a state of *nepantla* where they can either follow a path of *desconocimiento* or *conocimiento*. *Desconocimiento* results in assimilating to the dominant culture whereas *conocimiento* is a path “to reverse the colonization that has been passed on...through cultural practices and the construction of myths that operate in everyday discourse” (Orozco-Mendoza, 2008, p. 42). Taking the path of *conocimiento* allows one to imagine a reality beyond that of the dominant culture and provide a unique perspective of ways of being and knowing. Once on the path to *conocimiento*, however, *arrebatos* continuously occur, making the journey everlasting, where the path of *conocimiento* is only possible through the continuous healing from *arrebatos*.

Methods

46 Raza learners in third, fourth, and fifth grades across three predominantly white schools—more than 50% of the student population identifies as white while less than 20% of the student population identifies as Raza—in the south-eastern U.S. took part in a research collaboration. For this study, we focused on the 11 fourth grade learners who participated in one semi-structured interview ranging from 12 to 45 minutes. The interviews focused on the participants telling stories about their experiences regarding race, language, and mathematics. For example, participants were asked: Has there ever been a time you didn’t feel like you fit in because you identify as [nationality] (e.g., Mexican, Chilean, Argentine)? How does knowing Spanish help you in learning math? If your teacher could teach math in Spanish, would that be helpful to you? Why or why not? Following Latinx critical theory methodologies, we used a grounded theory approach to develop a composite counter-story based on Raza learners’ experiences.

There was a conscious effort to not adultify the Raza children, their discourse, and experiences; keeping in mind their understanding of race is different from adults (Quintana, 2007). Quintana (2007) argued most elementary age children either have a literal perspective of race where physical characteristics are the main criteria for one’s race, or a social perspective of race where “children begin integrating their own observations of their social world into their verbal reasoning about race” (Quintana, 2007, p. 26). The range of understanding of race needed to be considered as we conducted and analysed their interviews.

We use composite counter-storytelling (Solórzano & Yosso, 2001, 2002) to describe the experiences of the 11 fourth grade Raza learners with the Borderlands they inhabit, which allow them to learn and grow within multiple cultures. Composite counter-storytelling is a method used in critical race methodology to centre the experiences of People of Color and recognize individual narratives as experienced by a collective (Solórzano & Yosso, 2002). Therefore, composite counter-storytelling allows for a more complete understanding of the experiences of the Raza learners. Furthermore, race and language are vastly complex and unique experiences, however, composite counter-storytelling allows the overlay of individual experiences to provide a more complete understanding of systemic racism.

Following Solórzano and Yosso (2002), we incorporated a grounded theory approach (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) to understand how varying degrees of Latinidad and Anglo culture play a role in navigating predominantly white spaces. Through initial readings of the transcripts, we noted any utterances about context or language. We used data that was both similar across participants as well as unique experiences that stood out. These experiences became themes we used to explore for evidence in each of the other participants. After multiple iterations, these themes were combined or expanded upon to become codes that explain how language played a role in learning and doing mathematics for the Raza students. Following Solórzano and Yosso (2002) we paired the data from the interviews, various literature on Raza experiences, and our own anecdotal evidence to create a composite counter-story.

Composite counter-storytelling and Borderlands

The data from interviews with Raza learners guided our construction of a composite counter-story. Each of the themes were developed using the voices of the young Raza learners which became conversations with the research team relating our own anecdotal evidence to the data and literature. The utterances from the Raza learners were just a snapshot of larger stories, grounded within systems of power due to race and language (in this case). We could understand the experiences of the young Raza learners, because we too had similar experiences. Furthermore, we recognized larger systems of power in play when Mauricio said “there’s like not that much things to be talking about in Spanish during class”. This is an utterance, a small view into Mauricio’s experiences in learning math. However, it is grounded in systems of power around race and language, which we felt should be told through a composite counter-story for several reasons. As stated previously, composite counter-storytelling allows the voice of the Raza learner to be centred and access to various communities outside of academia. Furthermore, the composite aspect allows these utterances to be understood as embedded within other data, such as literature. In the example of Mauricio, his utterance provides a way to understand the effects of white superiority and how racism and linguicism play out in everyday life. In this section, we continue to highlight students’ utterances as moments of nepantla that guided our construction of a composite counter-story: a) Navigating location and audience; b) Value of the Spanish language; and c) Tensions of language in learning mathematics.

Navigating location and audience

Students often felt they needed to leave Spanish outside academic conversations while at school, however, they still identified with and used Spanish at lunch and recess. Therefore, navigating location and audience, where students must recognize safe spaces for using Spanish versus English, became an instance of nepantla. For example, Mauricio described not wanting to use Spanish in the classroom because he was afraid of getting caught, which guided his decision of when to use, and not use each language. Mauricio provides insight into how language is used against him, as a way to other and criminalize him for speaking Spanish. Raza students' entire linguistic repertoires, English, Spanish, and a mixture of the two languages, were used in other spaces such as their home, cultural events (i.e., fiestas), some stores (i.e., mercados), and with Spanish-speaking friends. We also acknowledge the depth of students' linguistic repertoire of being able to recognize their audience and make adjustments accordingly; however, they were also tasked with having to cross language borders of English, Spanish, and a hybrid of the two. For example, Carmen explained how she speaks Spanish with her parents, but English with her brother. Therefore, inhabiting a Borderland where she uses both Spanish and English depending on her audience.

Valuing of Spanish language

Raza students described another instance of nepantla as valuing the Spanish language. Students received messages from their parents that it is important to continue using Spanish because it is part of their culture. For example, Carmen discussed her father's desire for her to speak more Spanish, stating, "[my father] was saying let's just talk more Spanish because I'm like Spanish." The dominant narratives in schools, however, perpetuate English as the spoken language in the U.S. and required for academic purposes. Carmen and her father are finding ways to resist assimilation into the dominant culture and disrupt white supremacy. Furthermore, Mauricio had been led to believe Spanish is not an important language for academic purposes, stating, "there's like not that much things to be talking about in Spanish during class." Mauricio shows how white supremacist ideals of English-only spaces prevents him from using his entire linguistic repertoire. We see these two conflicting narratives told by Carmen and Mauricio to be a space where students are experiencing nepantla; they must make choices in each space about which parts of their linguistic identities to foreground.

Tensions of language in doing mathematics

Raza students also discussed navigating Borderlands of language in regard to the use of language in the mathematics classroom. Because mathematics was positioned as an English-only act in their schools, Spanish-speaking students negotiated their linguistic identities in order to navigate the mathematics classroom. Therefore, positioning Raza students as traversing the Spanish language along with the English-only norms of mathematics. Several students said they would like to learn mathematics in Spanish because it would help them learn more Spanish (Angelica, Estifan, Rocio). For example, when asked if learning math in Spanish would be helpful, Estifan stated, "Yeah... because then I would be able to speak Spanish anytime I wanted." Estifan desires to disrupt white supremacy and dominant

narratives of English-only norms in mathematics and valuing Spanish, often seen as deficit by educational institutions. Therefore, entering a state of *nepantla* where they must decide to either assimilate and use English-only, or push back and take a path of *conocimiento* where Spanish can be used as a resource in learning mathematics as well. For example, several students described their parents helping them learn mathematics in both English and Spanish. Specifically, Mauricio explained how he navigates these contradictions of language and mathematics by doing his mathematics homework in both Spanish and English. He provides his thinking in Spanish for his dad, but also does the work in English to prepare for class the next day. These narratives explain how Raza students value Spanish but are navigating an English-only mathematics classroom.

Conclusion

Using Borderlands theory to frame the composite counter-story of the 4th grade Raza students in predominantly white schools amplifies the unique experiences of navigating multiple cultures. The 11 Raza students shared multiple narratives regarding the negotiation of their linguistic repertoire. Within their Borderlands schooling pushes English-only academic spaces, while the home encourages the use of both languages to preserve their Spanish proficiency. Raza students must decide when, where, and how to make these negotiations in each space. Anzaldúa (1987) argues students in a place of *nepantla* choose to assimilate (*desconocimiento*) or disrupt dominant narratives and exist in multiple spaces and ways of knowing (*conocimiento*).

Asking students to assimilate into the dominant culture positions one culture superior to the other, forcing Raza students to make a decision to forego one culture over the other. In making that decision, however, one culture must be silenced. We wonder what it would mean for students to not have to decide, to not have to choose between cultures. We argue for the whole child to be accepted, seen as a resource, and able to exist as a hybrid of the cultures impacting their lives and learning of mathematics.

Finally, we can no longer ask 4th grade Raza students to navigate these spaces on their own; Raza students need support in learning about the cultures impacting their lives. This is not as simple as adding more Raza teachers, or other Teachers of Color to the workforce; the sole solution is not a mathematical one (Tate et al., 1993). Furthermore, this work goes beyond our schools; schools are one medium where racism and white supremacy are perpetuated, but these issues are systemic. While it is imperative for teachers and pre-service teachers to learn and be held accountable for the cultures of the students they teach, this cannot be the only way to address racism and white supremacy. There is also a necessity for the system and narratives in place which perpetuate white supremacy to be revealed, questioned, and dismantled. The Raza students have provided the knowledge of how they must navigate a system put in place beyond their discretion; thus, it is not their job to grapple with it, navigate inbetweenness, assimilate to one over the other, or to resolve these conflicts. Their work has been done, they have gifted us this knowledge, a glimpse into challenges, conflicts, and contradictions persistent in their lives. While we will keep fighting for and

providing counterstories of these injustices, it is time for those who benefit most from these systems to learn how to resolve and dismantle the system of exclusion of Raza and other Students of Color.

References

- Aguilar-Valdez, J. R., LópezLeiva, C. A., Roberts-Harris, D., Torres-Velásquez, D., Lobo, G., & Westby, C. (2013). Ciencia en Nepantla: The journey of Nepantler@s in science learning and teaching. *Cultural Studies of Science Education*, 8, 821–858.
- Anzaldúa, G. (1987). *Borderlands/La frontera: The new mestiza*. San Francisco, CA: Aunt Lute Books.
- Bell, D. (2018). *Faces at the bottom of the well: The permanence of racism*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Carbado, D. W., & Gulati, M. (2014). *Acting white? Rethinking race in "Post-Racial" America*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Delgado, R., & Stefancic, J. (2017). *Critical race theory: An introduction*. New York, NY: New York University Press.
- Dunbar-Ortiz, R. (1994). One or two things I know about us: "Okies" in American culture. *Radical History Review*, 59, 4–34.
- Flores, T. (2018). Chicas fuertes: Counterstories of Latinx parents raising strong girls. *Bilingual Research Journal*, 41(3), 329–348.
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory*. Chicago, IL: Aldine.
- Gutiérrez, J. A. (2001). *The making of a Chicano militant*. Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Ignatiev, N. (2009). *How the Irish became white*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Martin, D. B. (2015). The collective Black and *Principles to Actions*. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*, 8(1), 17–23.
- Martínez, E. (2017). *De colores means all of us: Latina views for a multicolored century*. Brooklyn, NY: Verso.
- Martínez, M. M. (2020). *The injustice never leaves you: Anti-Mexican violence in Texas*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Orozco, C. E. (2012). *No Mexicans, women or dogs allowed: The rise of the Mexican American civil rights movement*. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press.
- Orozco-Mendoza, E. F. (2008). Borderlands theory: Producing border epistemologies with Gloria Anzaldúa. [Master's thesis, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University]. https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/bitstream/handle/10919/32268/Final_thesis_corrected.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Quintana, S. M. (2008). Racial perspective taking ability: Development, theoretical, and empirical trends. In S. M. Quintana & C. McKown (Eds.), *Handbook of race, racism, and the developing child* (pp. 16–36). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Schiro, M. S. (2013). *Curriculum theory: Conflicting visions and enduring concerns*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Solórzano, D. G. (1998). Critical race theory, race and gender microaggressions, and the experiences of Chicana and Chicano scholars. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 11(1), 121–136.
- Solórzano, D. G., & Yosso, T. J. (2002). Critical race methodology: Counter-storytelling as an analytical framework for education research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 8(1), 23–44.
- Yancey, G. (2004). *Who is White? Latinos, Asians, and the new Black/Nonblack divide*. Boulder, CO: Lynne Rienner.
- Yosso, T. (2006). *Critical race counterstories along the Chicana/Chicano educational pipeline*. New York, NY: Routledge.